

Analysis of email phishing in session hijacking

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Abstract— *Phishing is a form of deception used by Internet users where attackers steal sensitive information via email, emails, messages or advertisements. These attachments may contain malicious software that could infect the user's device. If the user opens this URL, then a false website opens, in which the user enters confidential data. While fraudulent methods continue to be prevalent, the purpose of this study is to provide information on how to identify an infected email and educate users about the features of phishing emails. We structure our work based on the layout of phishing concepts and knowing how a phishing attack occurs.*

Keywords— **Session hijacking, phishing, attack, URL, email, link.**

I. INTRODUCTION

Session Hijacking is an attack on users by attackers in order to obtain confidential data [15]. Attackers try to launch attacks when users access the browser to perform actions such as checking credit card balance, buying products online or making online bill payments. They send links or emails to users in order for the latter to enter their sensitive data causing attackers to have control over their accounts.

Phishing is a method that attackers use to collect users personal information using malicious emails. It is very difficult to distinguish whether an email is phishing or not, so these attacks have become frequent and are considered the most dangerous attacks that occur today [3].

Phishing emails are a type of attack where social engineers lure the recipient to perform specific actions such as clicking on a link, opening an attachment or visiting a website and entering their personal information [1].

The attacker sends a URL to the user and when the user clicks on this URL a web page opens, making the user believe that the web page is legitimate, but in fact it is not. When a user enters their personal information into this newly opened site such as passwords, usernames or credit card numbers, the website stores this sensitive data and then sends it to the attacker [10].

Everyone needs to learn to protect themselves from this cyber attack. Attackers use fake emails in order to obtain sensitive data from users by making them believe that the link or website comes from a trusted source. Sometimes malware is downloaded to the user's computer. In some other cases phishing e-mail is sent which receives employee details to be used as an advanced attack against a specific company. Cyber-attacks, such as Permanent Advanced Threats (APT) and software rewards, usually begin with phishing [5] [17].

Phishing attacks are used for the purpose of providing usually sensitive information of the person/people attacked. The common way is manipulating the attacker into providing a website similar with legitimate ones. The strategy for doing this is that the attacker constructs a malicious site employing a phishing website. The information can be gathered and as a consequence may be provided to the attacker Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to analyze the concept of phishing email, to show how sensitive user data goes to attackers through links coming to emails and finally to make the reader know if an email is phishing or not.

This paper is organized in this way. "Introduction" offers some definitions of phishes and how phishing occurs. Presents ideas of other works comparing them with our work in the "Related Work" section, continues with the background, which presents in detail the concept of phishing and shows how to distinguish a legitimate URL from the illegitimate one. The following section is "Evaluation" where an example of email phishing is presented experimentally and closes with the conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

Phishing is a broad topic that is mostly used in cyber security and is often used as a first step in ongoing advanced threats. In addition, there are many works by different authors that address and analyze the topic of phishing emails.

The authors in the paper [6] discuss a variety of phishing attacks and ways to stop these attacks. Here are some techniques for preventing social engineering attacks including phishing attacks, as well as the methodology, advantages and disadvantages of these techniques. One solution they offer for these attacks is that the user the moment a suspicious link comes to them should copy the link and open it on a new page. This way it tells the user whether the website he came across is legal or not. Today there are a considerable number of free internet sites which show the authenticity of the websites. Furthermore, algorithms are found that indicate whether an attack is phishing or not, such as link protection algorithm and surf detector.

The paper [7] unlike other works uses the decision tree algorithm to find out if the newly received email is involved in a phishing attack or not. This algorithm is based on the Gmail account because after a survey they concluded that Gmail is the most common account where these attacks can occur. In addition, according to the authors this system can also generate fraud report to the user. The use of Anti-Phishing methods is done in order to detect, identify and block these fraudulent websites. This project has used the Agile Unified Process (AUP) methodology in for the main purpose of calculating the percentages of phishing emails stored in the user's emails.

The paper [4] discusses the different types of phishing attacks, addresses the term attack vectors, and presents some techniques that make it possible to detect phishing attacks.

The techniques this paper uses are list-based techniques, based on heuristic, visual similarity, and machine learning. Also is made comparison of the performance of different techniques in relation to data sets, including 18 different models along with 9 sources.

The scheme proposed in the paper [8] addresses the existing database to identify phishes committed by attackers. In addition to identifying the author also tries to prevent these attacks from occurring in the future by blocking emails or messages. The scheme that this paper proposes is a combination of supervised and unsupervised machine learning in order to identify and prevent phishing attacks both new and old. This scheme assigns specific tasks to each technique where the supervised technique identifies all behaviors, signatures or channels known to the attacker and the unsupervised technique which captures any anomalous action that occurs during normal internet communication.

Thesis [9], reviews various anti-phishing concepts and methods. This paper discusses all methods in order to give a clearer idea of the techniques that already exist, the limitations that these methods have and what improvements they can offer. Another thing that is analyzed in this paper are the tools of using anti-phishing. After much research it has been concluded that these tools are ineffective in detecting all places where phishing occurs, especially those that have just been registered. Also outlined are some important steps that need to be taken to build a complete and useful anti-phishing model, where all this is done through the architecture diagram. The paper concludes with a comparison of models using 5 types of approaches based on the accuracy and size of the data resulting in an efficient model of deep learning is preferred to be suggested because it aims to give a better performance than other methods.

The paper [11] as well as any other paper has as its main purpose the detection of these phishing attacks. Their work is based on the design and development of a new model in order to detect these attacks using machine learning techniques. After a review to get better acquainted with the types of emails that are infected with phishing have formed a scheme based on the combination of algorithms Naive Bayes and Decision tree. All of this is done using the typical Machine Learning (ML) modeling cycle. The main tools used were the Jupiter and Python frames. All testing was initially done in a controlled environment and the infected emails were retrieved via PhishTank. In conclusion, to be

more accurate and secure, the results were verified using algorithms such as ML Random Forest, Regression Logistic and Fictitious Classifier. Also different assessments by Singh [12] use the same machine learning technique in order to detect and detect phishing attacks in other words to see if the incoming emails are legal or not.

The models presented by the machine learning technique are used to understand the types of websites differently to separate legitimate websites from phishing ones. The paper [13] presents a method based on a feature vector in order to understand whether a website displays attacks or not. This paper uses the J48 algorithm in order to obtain an estimate in the detection of phishing attacks.

A model based on detecting a phishing website by analyzing submitted URLs has been studied by Chatterjee [14]. Since the model itself is self-adapting to changes in the URL structure shows a problem and in order to eliminate this problem a method based on the use of deep neural network has been used. To see how good it is as a performance measurement model using accuracy, recall and measurement F.

In research [16], the concepts of "Artificial Neural Network (ANN)" features have been used in order to make a more accurate classification. In this project, 15 unique features of a URL are extracted where exactly these features are trained in an artificial network. All of this is then used to classify a phishing website. The resulting learning model is then applied to classify a phishing website.

III. BACKGROUND

Phishing attacks are used for the purpose of providing usually sensitive information of the person/people attacked. The common way is manipulating the attacker into providing a website similar with legitimate ones. The strategy for doing this is that the attacker constructs a malicious site employing a phishing website. The information can be gathered and as a consequence may be provided to the attacker.

Phishing is a social engineering attack form that typically starts with an email. The email attack aims the recipient into clicking a URL, which is originally infected to look legitimate in design for the user.

If the user clicks on it and enter the information, usually sensitive data including passwords or credit card data, the website register the data to send them to the attacker.

On purpose of detecting new attacks are observed data and phishing attacks that have occurred before with features similar to the attack being studied. There are some tests that are taken to understand if a URL is phishing:

- if a part of URL host - name is similar with an IP address
- if the URL path contains the company name, but the main domain does not contain it typically when password field is shown in a web page

Since web pages are different, every web page should have an address which is called a URL. Uniform Resource Locator (URL) is the term used to determine the global addresses of documents or any other source on the Internet. A URL consists of three main parts: hostname, path and protocol. The hostname is a label used to specify the server of the resource location, the path refers to the location of the page and is written after hostname. The protocol is used for data transfer between the host and the web browser.

URL STRUCTURE

A URL is determined as a unique address for a specific resource on the internet. To better understand the structure of the URL we take an example as follows:

https://kryeministria.al/Newsletter/newsletter.html

1. Scheme: This is used to distinguish which protocol is used for accessing the resources. The protocol shows how a browser should regain information about a resource. Common protocols are HTTP /HTTPS.

2. Host: It is the name used to identify the machine that serves as the resource host. In the previous example, kryeministria.al acts as the hostname. Host names may be followed by a port number.

3. Path: This represents a path that displays the exact location of the source on the host. The path indicates the specific resource in the host that the client aims to access. In the example that we are studying, the resource is found at the location “/Newsletter/newsletter.html”.

4. Query: The question string is usually optional, located after the path and provides further specific information.

EMAIL STRUCTURE

An email is constructed in two main parts: Header and Body.

1. Header

Headers are the first important part of building an email that gives us general information about the sender and recipient. Some headers are mandatory (From, To) and some optional (CC).

Despite the main purpose, the header can provide some information about the path taken to transfer data between computers.

2. Body features: In the body part we have more detailed information regarding the subject of the email. Despite the fact that emails can be written in a reliable way, researchers have noticed some common phrases used in phishing emails such as: Click Below, Warning, Notice, Winner, Urgent etc.

Sender Policy Framework (SPF) is a used for phishing detections operating with its mechanisms, qualifiers and modifiers. SPF can detect a forged sender claim of the email and combined with DMARC can be used to detect email spoofing.

IV. EVALUATION

In this Section, is shown the experiment on email phishing example.

SET is an attack system based on attack on human resources that comes pre-installed on Kali Linux using command "setoolkit". Despite the variety of attacks, this toolkit is absolutely essential for penetration testing. It offers help in creating a phishing page by copying the original.

Mass Mailer Attack can allow you to use it as an attack against some users and if necessary, even using a list of users. This command is open to using a Gmail account or even a server for mass attack.

In this example we used an email, including a phishing website corresponding to Google. In the example the page "kryeministria.al" the official government website is used and the winner of the competition is asked to go to the Google page to continue. If the target writes the data then, email and password are displayed causing the basic data to be retrieved by the attacker. A real attack would require more attention to both email structure and text design, to be more accurate to the original website. To perform this attack firstly we go to Kali Linux, enter setoolkit command, then social

engineering attack, Mass Mailer Attack, E-Mail Attack Single Email Address and then we perform the instruction on figure 1 in order to complete a mail with its header and body. We send the email including a phishing URL based on Google Account.


```
1. E-Mail Attack Single Email Address
2. E-Mail Attack Mass Mailer

## Return to main menu.

setoolkit>
setoolkit> Send email to:provea22@gmail.com

1. Use a gmail Account for your email attack.
2. Use your own server or open relay

setoolkit>
setoolkit> your gmail email address:suptec2389@gmail.com
setoolkit> The FROM NAME the user will see:ALBANIAN GOVERNMENT
Email password:
setoolkit> Flag this message/s as high priority? [yes/no]:n
Do you want to attach a file - [y/n]:n
Do you want to attach an inline file - [y/n]:n
setoolkit> Email subject:Winner!
setoolkit> Send the message as html or plain? 'h' or 'p' [p]:p
[!] IMPORTANT: when finished, type END (all capital) then hit (return) on a new line.
setoolkit> Enter the body of the message, type END (capital) when finished:Congrats,you are chosen from plat
form "shqiperiaone.al"
Next line of the body: please visit the link below for more information.
Next line of the body: http://10.0.2.15
Next line of the body: Thank you for your application!
Next line of the body: END
[!] SET has finished sending the emails

Press ctrl+c to continue
```

Figure 1: Kali Linux Commands for email phishing

The information that we entered using Toolkit Social Engineering Attack will show on the email that we sent.

This includes the fake winner announcement that we use in order to attack the target. The email has a phishing URL and goes to Google Login Form.

Figure 2: Email with infected URL

If we click the link that we infected, we have to login on Google account.

characteristics used to discover infected emails and to prevent being a victim from phishing.

This review helped us to understand the realization of email phishing using illegitimate URL-s and to be more careful from the risks that can follow from phishing methods in general.

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Figure 3: Login to fake Google Account

If the target clicks Sign In the information that was entered will show on the figure.4.

```
PARAM: utf8=
PARAM: bgresponse=js_disabled
PARAM: pstMsg=1
PARAM: dnConn=
PARAM: checkConnection=
PARAM: checkedDomains=youtube
POSSIBLE USERNAME FIELD FOUND: Email=provea22@gmail.com
POSSIBLE PASSWORD FIELD FOUND: Passwd=detyre1
PARAM: signIn=Sign-in
PARAM: PersistentCookie=yes
[!] WHEN YOU'RE FINISHED, HIT CONTROL-C TO GENERATE A REPORT.
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Figure 4: Login data information that attacker received

V. CONCLUSION

There are many different techniques to phishing attacks and the one that we studied is based on email.

Phishing is a social engineering security attack that attempts to trick targets into reveal sensitive information. Using an infected URL, attackers target users' login credentials, financial information and other valuable information. In this paper we performed an attack using some commands from Kali Linux in order to provide information about the victim. We identified the main

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